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#STI2022GRX

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#STI22GRX

The multilingual aspect of citation contexts¹

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Research questions

English is the language of reference among scientists. Dissemination in a dominant language, such as English, necessarily influences the production of knowledge and this can have a number of consequences especially in the evaluative metrics for scientific research. The fairness of scientific research evaluation depends to a large extent on the comprehensiveness and accuracy of citation data. English has a greater influence in the scientific field, it is inevitable that language bias will result in an unfair evaluation of the impact of scientific research indicators on other languages' research. This makes English more and more dominant in knowledge dissemination, while gradually weakening the influence of other languages in terms of scientific development. (Márquez & Porrás, 2020) are investigating the consequences of the use of English as the international language of science.

However, while English has had a form of hegemony in recent decades, this has not always been the case (Gordin, 2015). Russian, French and German, to name but a few, are still used to produce scientific concepts. Indeed, we think in our language and concepts vary with linguistic diversity and different cultures. Building science means building concepts and this is done through dialogue, controversy and scientific debate. The question that arises is: do we mobilise concepts identically from one language to another? Conversely, can the same notions and concepts be produced and defined identically if they are formulated in different languages?

Within the context of this study, we are particularly interested in the study of citation acts and more particularly the study of citation contexts, which represents an interdisciplinary theme (Moravcsik, 1975), (Small, 1982), (White, 2004), (Teufel et al. 2006), (Abu-Jbara et al., 2013), (Ciancarini, 2014). Indeed, it requires knowledge in bibliometry but also in computer science and automatic language processing. The study of citation contexts implies the study of references present in the text and the study of their contexts. Numerous studies have been carried out in this area, attempting to establish a semantic dimension to the nature of the relations involved.

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Through the multilingual study of citation contexts, we wish to better understand the semantic dimension in order to better think about multilingualism within scholarly communication.

Discussion of methods and techniques

dataset

Within the context of this study, we have selected various projects and resources that allow us to build a multilingual corpus. There are therefore many multilingual resources of scientific articles. In our project, we have selected several databases in order to build a multilingual corpus. We can mention ISTEEX, which is a reservoir of scientific archives at the service of French research, covering all disciplines with more than 25 million scientific publications and spanning a period of 700 years (Collignon, Cuxac. 2017).

There are also many German language resources in the field of science and more recently in the field of social sciences with the EXCITE project (Hosseini et al., 2019). The EXCITE project has developed a software tool chain for citation extraction that will be applied to existing databases of scientific literature and made available to researchers with a special focus on the German-speaking social sciences.

We can also make use of the PLOS dataset which is composed of 7 journals in English in the field of science, technology and medicine. As the amount of published scientific literature increases, to explore essences of these researches and advance science, PLOS encourages publishers to open their content for the purpose of supporting the analysis of scientific articles by the method of text and data mining (Kamińska. 2017).

Natural Language Processing and Multilingualism

From a technological implementation point of view, one of the main challenges in automatic language processing and multilingual information retrieval is to develop general language-independent architectures that will be equally applicable to any language. This creates a number of difficulties such as the structural and semantic properties of the world's languages. One must also consider the scarcity of raw data and heavy tasks of annotation of corpus for many languages, which creates a lack of resources to process by some automated text mining methods. Through transfer learning, even in the case of very little labeled data, we can still get good task performance with the help of pre-trained language models.

Pires et al. (2019) showed that the Multilingual BERT (mBERT), released by (Devlin et al., 2019) as a single language model pre-trained from monolingual corpora in 104 languages, is surprisingly good at zero-shot cross-lingual model transfer. Pretrained multilingual text encoders based on neural transformer architectures, such as mBERT and XLM (Conneau and Lample 2019; Conneau et al. 2020a), have recently become a default paradigm for cross-lingual transfer of natural language processing models (Litschko, Vulić, Ponzetto and Glavaš, 2022). But (Joshi et al., 2020) has proposed that unsupervised pre-training methods only make the "poor poorer" because there is little unlabelled data to work with. Due to the limited capacity of the unsupervised pre-trained model, the transfer performance is weakest on such low-resource languages and languages not seen during pre-training (Pfeiffer et al., 2020). For this reason, we need to build up a sufficiently significant corpus of scientific articles in a more appropriate way which could improve cross-lingual transfer performance.

The latest scientific research in this field mobilizes different techniques. For example, the following research represents the latest developments in this area. (Pfeiffer et al., 2020) propose

MAD-X, an adapter-based framework that enables high portability and parameter-efficient transfer to arbitrary tasks and languages by learning modular language and task representations. In order to improve the performance of adapter modules for the vast majority languages, (Ansell et al. 2021) propose the MAD-G (Multilingual ADapter Generation) approach. It contextually generates language adapters from linguistic representations based on typological features. In addition to adapter-based methods, (Litschko, Vulić, and Glavaš. 2022) show another parameter-efficient approach namely Sparse Fine-Tuning Masks (SFTMs), allow for a more lightweight and more effective zero-shot transfer to multilingual and cross-lingual retrieval tasks.

Perspectives

In this work, we wish to highlight the semantics of citation contexts across the different scientific languages mobilised. To do so, it is necessary to build ontologies dedicated to the different languages studied and to mobilise multilingual annotation techniques in order to propose an identification capacity of the different citation acts according to the citation contexts.

The main objective is to define whether the act of citations mobilizes the same notions from one language to another, which are identified through the contexts of citations. Through this research, we will provide a better understanding of language issues and their consideration in bibliometrics. We will echo the Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication.

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